

Ultrasonic welding of metal and fibre reinforced thermoplastics – bond formation and joint strength

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Ultrasonic welding of multi-material joints

- Motivation

Basics of ultrasonic welding

- Types of ultrasonic welding

polymer ultrasonic welding

metal ultrasonic welding

Basics of ultrasonic welding

- Oscillation system

- Initiate an oscillation by inverse piezo electric effect close to the natural frequency of the system
- Acoustic translation of the boosters and the sonotrode affect the resulting amplitude at the sonotrode tip

Basics of ultrasonic welding

- Industrial applications of ultrasonic welding

packaging materials

thermoplastic bodies

metallic foils

electric conductors

solar collectors

Basics of ultrasonic POLYMER welding

- Joint and interface formation

- single material or blend by melting and diffusion

Interface Model

Molecular Model

Zhang, H., Lamnawar, K. & Maazouz, A. Rheological modeling of the diffusion process and the interphase of symmetrical bilayers based on PVDF and PMMA with varying molecular weights. *Rheol Acta* **51**, 691–711 (2012).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00397-012-0629-7>

Basics of ultrasonic METAL welding

- Joint and interface formation

1. Shearing off topographic peaks
2. Breaking up oxide layers
3. Pure metal/metal contact
4. Interlocking by plastic deformation

- metallurgical multi-metal joints by plastic deformation and diffusion

1. Fusing of thermoplastic matrix
2. Approximation of metal and fibres
3. Interlocking of metal and fibres

- adhesive bonding
- mechanical interlocking by plastic deformation
- and ?

Multi-material Ti6Al4V/CF-PEEK-joints – Orbital ultrasonic welding

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Multi-material Ti6Al4V/CF-PEEK-joints - Interface formation and strength

- No fibre-metal-contact
- Insufficient amount of welding energy to form high strength joint
- Fibre-metal-contact
- No cavities
- ➔ Suitable process parameters
- Large cavities
- PEEK decomposition

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FE modelling of Multi-material-joints - Overview

- **Interface characterisation and categorisation**
- **FE-Simulations of real 2D structures**
- **FE-Simulations of 3D models**

Arweiler-Böllert, S., Liesegang, M., Beck, T. *et al.* Relation Between Interface Geometry and Tensile Shear Strength of Ultrasonically Welded Joints. *J. of Materi Eng and Perform* **32**, 10469-10485 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-023-08325-2>

Sophie Arweiler

FE modelling of Multi-material-joints - Categorisation of interface structures

lower mechanical strength

higher mechanical strength

FE modelling of Multi-material-joints

- External Loading and Boundary Conditions

Calculation of the displacement in the microsection using the results from the tensile shear tests

FE modelling of Multi-material-joints

- Contact Model and Contact Conditions

bilinear traction-separation law

- K_{eff} – contact stiffness
- T_m – maximum traction; start of contact damage
- δ_t – total separation between 2 nodes

Variation of the contact conditions by varying T_m :

FE modelling of Multi-material-joints

- Correlation between joint strength and interface geometry

 bonded

FE modelling of Multi-material-joints - Outlook

- in-situ μ -CT-scans during loading
- FE-Simulations of real 3D structures

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Thank you!

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